

Marine Litter Classification Through Multi-Camera System: Perception and Latency

B. Jalil*, L. Maggiani[†], L. Valcarengi*

* Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna, Pisa, Italy

[†] Sma-rtly Italia s.r.l, Italy

e-mail: bushra.jalil@santannapisa.it

Abstract—This work presents a pilot study to classify marine litter observed through a distributed static camera system. The acquisition from the multi-camera sources located at different viewpoints transmits data to the edge devices for independent, low-latency image classification. We employed transfer learning-based networks to monitor moving objects using a dataset sourced from the JAMSTEC library of Deep-Sea images for training purposes. The pre-trained VGG19, ResNet50, and DenseNet121 network architectures are employed as fixed feature extractors to train on underwater marine dataset. The achieved accuracies are 78%, 83%, and 84% respectively on test data. We further simulated, through the experimental setup, the impact of latency on the performance of classification output when the video streams from two cameras arrive at the edge device with different delays.

Index Terms—Edge computing, Convolution Neural Networks (CNN), multi-camera, marine litter, latency, classification

I. INTRODUCTION

Human-created waste thrown into the sea or nearby is extremely harmful to the health and safety of marine life. This waste enters the sea or oceans through multiple sources, including food packaging, plastic bottles, food, and drinks cans, among others *etc.* [1]. Most importantly, glass or metal lying at the bottom of the sea is harmful for deep-sea divers and can contaminate water as well. In certain situations, these sharp objects block boat propellers and ultimately lead to expensive repairs. Therefore, it is extremely important to identify and quantify these densely polluted areas, compare data from continually observed systems, and finally take actions based on monitoring outcomes. Traditionally, monitoring of marine pollution is performed through in-situ visual census, which is time-consuming and requires more human effort. However, with the advancement of complex artificial intelligence algorithms in daily routine tasks, the efficient and effective solution would be to track these densely polluted areas through systems. These systems, equipped with embedded devices based on state-of-the-art AI algorithms, mounted on Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) or Unmanned Surface Vehicles (USVs), can be an effective solution to overcome the problems of marine litter monitoring [2].

During the last few years, significant efforts have been directed towards addressing the problem of marine litter monitoring in an automated manner. In this regard, due to the availability of a vast number of images acquired in real environments and the possibility to generate synthetic data

from available images and later incorporate them with real images, Deep Learning (DL)-based algorithms are widely used in the detection and classification of marine litter. Several techniques have been proposed in recent years. Canals et al. provided a detailed review of some of these methods, outlining existing needs, and identifying open challenges for the estimation of seafloor marine litter [3], for future developments. The authors also provided detailed background knowledge of ocean modeling techniques. Mattis et al. presented a machine learning algorithm based on convolutional neural networks to detect and quantify floating plastic litter [4]. Similarly, Politikos et al. detected seafloor marine litter in a real-world environment using a Region-based Convolution Neural Network [5]. Also, Marin et al. developed a model for autonomous marine debris identification and classification [2]. They also compared state-of-the-art deep convolutional architectures for marine debris classification. Toro et al. designed a two-step CNN architecture using sliding window techniques for the use of Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) to detect underwater marine litter [6]. More recently, Lieshout et al. demonstrated an automated technique for tracking plastic pollution in the sea [7]. Their method initially segments the region of interest followed by the detection. Several other techniques based on CNN models also exist to classify marine debris. However, making the complete process automated is still a challenging problem due to the type and significant in-class variations. Several objects are similar in shape (such as plastic or glass bottles, plastic cups, and metallic cans, etc.) belonging to different classes (e.g., as shown in Fig. 2 where the same object can be classified into multiple classes). On the other hand, objects including plastic bottles, plastic bags, and cups are very different in shape but belong to the same class. Similarly, the acquisition of the same object from a different view influences the performance of the method. In this study, we demonstrate this through the experimental setup that the object appears differently when viewed from another angle. A possible solution to address these issues could be a multi-camera system which acquires data from different views simultaneously using more than one camera and later, by applying data fusion techniques, provides a more reliable and robust solution. Camera networks are deployed for various surveillance and tracking applications, as explained in [8]–[10], where video streams from multiple cameras are acquired and sent to the central location for processing.

The outcomes of these systems are generally delayed and require more resources to process the incoming stream at the centralized location, making them computationally expensive. In literature, very limited study related to the impact of delay during real-time acquisition is given. It is extremely important to monitor and adjust the latency issues in the case of real-time monitoring. With recent advancements in the field of artificial intelligence and applications in routine tasks, the effective solution is to track densely polluted areas through AI-based embedded devices mounted on unmanned vehicles, which can perform the task of locating and classifying litter objects simultaneously, while reducing the overall monitoring time and cost. During this process, it is also important to integrate the information gathered through different devices and process them in real time without data offloading. Due to faster data transmission rates and lower latency, 5G networks provide a new dimension to connect multiple devices and sensors to perform tasks in an automated or semi-automated manner, even when located in remote positions. Traditionally, with cloud computing, the data acquired from different devices are stored and processed at remote servers, which require higher bandwidth and have relatively higher latency issues. The impact of latency is extremely important to consider in the case of time-critical data, such as live video streaming, health applications, *etc.* Additionally, the delay can reduce the performance when multiple sensors are directly connected to the Cloud for the given task. Edge computing, an emerging technology, allows processing data near its source and, as a result, provides faster communication between different sensors and devices employed for the same task. It reduces the amount of data transmitted to the network and can provide approximately real-time processing due to shorter response delays. In this paper, with the aim of performing edge classification, we present our initial study on these issues, including the performance of AI algorithms when viewed from a single sensor and how the perspective of data acquisition influences the results, if data is perceived from different views and arrives at the edge device with different delays. We demonstrate through the experimental setup that the object (metallic trash) moving between cameras with different viewpoints can be wrongly perceived and directly influence the performance of classification. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section I introduces the subject and gives the background. The details of the dataset and experimental setup are given in Section II. In Section III, the detailed explanation of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and the architecture based on them is mentioned. Section IV discusses the results obtained through the network training and testing. We evaluate the performance on the video stream of multiple cameras viewing the same object from different perspectives (viewpoints) and how the moving object is perceived in each camera. Lastly, we discuss the latency issue on the performance. Section V finally concludes the paper with challenges and future extensions of the work.

Fig. 1. Sample of raw images of each class sourced from JAMSTEC-library of Deep-Sea images.

Fig. 2. Experimental setup: Images were acquired from two fixed D-Link IP cameras, capturing the moving object from different angles. These acquired images were then transmitted to a nearby computing device for processing.

II. MATERIALS METHODS

A. Acquisition and Dataset

The dataset used in this work is derived from the database of "The Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology (JAMSTEC)" [11]. They provided the Deep-sea Debris Database, which contains several marine debris videos and images available for litter object detection [12]. The dataset contains a total of 1,918 images belonging to six classes: Glass, Metal, Plastic, Rubber, Other, and No Trash. The litter objects were identified manually and labeled for each class. Fig. 1 illustrates a few images belonging to the six classes. Algorithms based on neural networks require a large amount of data to function properly, and this is the main bottleneck of these algorithms. The most general solution to address these issues is to generate synthetic data from available images and incorporate them with the real images, termed as data augmentation. We applied multiple data augmentation techniques including rotation, zoom, and shear to increase the number and diversity of training images. It is worth mentioning here that rotating images does not fulfill the gap of different perspectives or viewing angles, which is one of the main concepts to explore in this work. To test the classification model through a distributed camera system in approximately real-time and environment, we acquired a series of time-stamped image sequences of litter objects. The images were captured with two fixed D-Link IP cameras viewing the moving object from different angles, as explained in Fig. 2. The time-stamped video of approximately 10 seconds is recorded with 30 frames per second from two cameras. During acquisition, the data acquired through both cameras associates the new acquisition with the existing frames, and

Fig. 3. Illustration of the proposed transfer learning-based classification model. Pretrained models, such as VGG19, ResNet50, etc., trained on large datasets, are used as fixed feature extractors. The fully connected (FC) layers of the pretrained model are then trained with the new dataset for the target domain [15].

in the end, we acquired a total of 320 time-stamped frames from each camera.

III. DEEP LEARNING MODELS

A. Proposed Approach

The distributed multi-camera object classification system can be formalized as follows. Let $P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n\}$ be the moving objects, the number of objects present in the scene can be multiple and unknown, in the present work we consider classifying a single object at a time. $C = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_k\}$ be the vector of arbitrarily placed fixed cameras monitoring from different views (in the present study two IP cameras monitors a single object) at time $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_j\}$. The vector of measurement of camera $c \in C$ at time t is denoted by $X(c, t) = \{x_{c,t}^1, x_{c,t}^2, \dots, x_{c,t}^l\}$, $l \in \mathbb{Z}$ where t corresponds to the time at which the images were acquired. Measurement obtained from the cameras are calibrated and approximately synchronized. The resulting vector of all the measurements from multiple cameras at time t is denoted by $X(C, t) = \{x_{c,t}|c\}$ and the complete acquisition during the time period T is denoted $X(C, T) = \{x_{C,t}|1 \leq t \leq T\}$, where $c \in C$. The objective of this work is to classify object p from $x_{c,t}$ at each instant t [11].

B. Classification of litter

A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a deep Learning algorithm, the most extensively studied network architecture, which can take in an input image, assign weights and biases to the objects in the image and able to differentiate them from each other with better accuracy as compared to the other classification algorithms [2], [12]. Gua *et al.* provided an extensive survey of the recent advances in the field of CNN [12]. The convolutional layer aims to learn feature representations of the inputs and is composed of several convolution kernels to compute different feature maps. Specifically, each neuron of a feature map is connected to a region of neighbouring neurons in the previous layer. Such a neighbourhood is referred as the

receptive field in the previous layer. The feature map were obtained by convolving the input image with a learned kernel and by applying an element-wise nonlinear activation function on the convolved results to generate each feature map, the kernel is shared by all spatial locations of the input. The complete feature maps are obtained by using several different kernels. Mathematically, the feature value at location (i, j) in the k -th feature map of l -th layer, $z_{i,j,k}^l$, is calculated by:

$$z_{i,j,k}^l = w_k^l T x_{i,j}^l + b_k^l \quad (1)$$

where w_k^l and b_k^l are the weight vector and bias term of the k -th filter of the l -th layer respectively, and $x_{i,j}^l$ is the input patch centered at location (i, j) of the l -th layer. The activation value $a_{i,j,k}^l$ of convolutional feature $z_{i,j,k}^l$ can be computed as:

$$a_{i,j,k}^l = a(z_{i,j,k}^l) \quad (2)$$

The pooling layers aggregate information within the feature map by replacing local pooling regions with the maximum element in the case of max pooling. Training deep neural networks accurately requires a large amount of diverse annotated data. Collecting such a dataset, especially for marine litter classification, is expensive, difficult, and time-consuming [2]. An alternative solution is to use a transfer learning-based approach, where the model is pre-trained on the features of 1.2 million training images from 1000 classes of ImageNet datasets, which can classify limited classes of litter data. The schematic illustration of transfer learning is given in Fig. 3, where the pre-trained model transfers source domain parameters to the classification of marine debris. We use the pre-trained network as a fixed feature extractor and freeze all the convolutional layers, while training only the last fully connected dense layers of the network followed by the last softmax layers with 6 neurons [2]. The obtained feature vector sizes are 512, 1024, and 2048 for VGG19, DenseNet121, and ResNet50, respectively.

Model	Parameters	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)
VGG19	20.02M	78.43	79.51
ResNet-50	23.59M	84.15	83.55
DenseNet121	7.04M	83.95	85.38

TABLE I

Fig. 4. Normalized confusion matrix of DenseNet121, epoch = 100, Batch size of 16.

IV. SIMULATIONS AND DISCUSSION

We investigated well-known network architectures including ResNet, DenseNet121, and VGG19 for litter object classification using transfer learning. On top of the fixed layers used for feature extraction, a new classifier based on a new neural network is added to learn underlying patterns from extracted features of litter images and discriminate data according to them. Networks were trained using Keras on top of TensorFlow 2.2, a deep learning framework used within the Google Colab online environment for training and testing neural network architectures. As explained in the previous section, a transfer learning approach was applied to well-known architectures (ResNet50, VGG19, and DenseNet121) with pre-trained weights downloaded from the Keras library, which were then trained as a fixed feature extractor scheme on the litter dataset. For training purposes, we kept the batch size as 16 and used the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001, $\beta_1 = 0.9$, and $\beta_2 = 0.999$. To increase the size of the dataset, we applied augmentation techniques including random rotations, shearing, and flipping during training. We trained all models for 100 epochs while tuning the batch sizes.

To evaluate the performance of the classification algorithm, the two evaluation parameters are considered: accuracy and precision, formulated as follows:

$$Accuracy = \left\{ \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \right\} \quad (3)$$

$$Precision = \left\{ \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \right\} \quad (4)$$

Table I summarizes the evaluation of three models on the test data, where ResNet50 and DenseNet121 reached test accuracy of nearly 84% in 100 epoch and VGG19 reached 78% on test data. In all models, we observed increase in average test accuracy when batch size is reduced while keeping rest of the hyper parameters constant. In this work, all network architectures are used as fixed feature extractor scheme and can further be improved with fine tuning of few layers of the feature extractor at the cost of more complexity and computational time. To test the classification of moving objects in real time and environment, we deployed DenseNet121 with the test accuracy of 84% and fewest parameter count and make them an efficient choice among all. The Confusion matrix of the DenseNet121 on the google based test images is shown in Fig. 4, where *Rubber*, *Plastic* and *Glass* are correctly classified.

For simulation purposes, we acquired data from two IP cameras viewing the same object from different angles while the object was continuously in motion. For performance evaluation through simulations, we selected a cylindrical metallic object belonging to the Metallic class. However, while in motion, it can be classified as Rubber when viewed from the top surface due to similar shape features. The images were acquired at 30 frames per second for approximately 10 seconds. We estimated an average delay of approximately 4 milliseconds in acquisition from both cameras. As an example, some of the acquired images and obtained classification outputs are shown in Fig. 5. It is important to note here that the top surface of the metallic cylindrical object has a circular shape, similar to the Rubber object class, and ultimately, at instances where the camera views the circular side of the object, it is classified as Rubber. We further investigated this behavior and its impact on the data arrival at edge devices in the case of real-time monitoring of litter data. We compared the classification results obtained from both cameras at each instant.

Fig. 5 indicates the respective positions of the object acquired from both cameras at multiple instances. It is evident that the classification output fluctuates between the Metallic and Rubber classes, as explained previously, due to the similar shape feature. The dotted area represents the time when the object is neither facing the side cylindrical nor the top circular surface in both cameras, ultimately causing high instability in the output. Through this experimental setup, we evaluated the performance of the model in real-time applications with distributed cameras. It is observed that acquisitions from diverse angles can change the perspective of the same object, and with a single camera, it is extremely difficult to detect the moving object more precisely. Therefore, it is important to integrate the information acquired from more than one camera not only to provide a more robust solution but also to detect multiple objects. The statistical evaluation of the classification model on the data acquired from each camera is performed through the accuracy of the output as:

Fig. 5. Classification obtained from both camera at different time t . The images indicate the position of object at that instant t .

$$Classification\ Error(\epsilon) = \left\{ \frac{Errors}{Total\ Detection} \right\} \quad (5)$$

$$Accuracy = 1 - error(\epsilon) \quad (6)$$

Fig. 6. Obtained accuracy from *Camera 1* and *Camera 2* without delay. Transitions correspond to the instances where neither of the camera facing top circular surface

In Fig. 6, we present the accuracy in the case where acquisition arrives at the edge device from both cameras without any delay, considering both with and without the unstable area. We observed reduced accuracy in the dotted area where neither the side cylindrical nor the top circular surface is visible in the cameras. Camera 2, viewing more of the side cylindrical surface, achieved higher accuracy compared to the other, due to the fact that more surface area of the object is visible. Overall, in approximate real-time acquisition through both cameras, we were able to detect the object. However, in certain situations, it may not be possible to transmit data without any delay. If consensus-based monitoring is performed

in real-time, where information from one device is shared with the other, even a minor delay in data transmission can deteriorate the overall performance of the system because the information from one sensor is shared with the other to perform coordinated actions. We simulated this effect on the performance evaluation of independent classification models.

	Time t of Acquisition											Acquisition			
	t_0	t_1	t_2	t_3	t_4	t_5	t_6	t_7	t_8	t_9	-		-	-	t_{n-1}
Ideal (0 delay)	x_1	x_2	x_3	x_4	x_5	x_6	x_7	x_8	x_9	x_{10}	-	-	-	x_{n-1}	x_n
Real (Δ (ms) delay)	x_1	x_1	x_2	x_2	x_3	x_3	x_4	x_4	x_5	x_5	x_6	x_6	-	-	-

x_1 Acquisition at respective instance Buffered Value

Fig. 7. Explanation of delayed image sequence acquisition. *ideal* correspond to the sequence of images acquired without any time delay and *real* correspond to the delayed sequence of images

We acquired delayed image sequences as explained in Fig. 7 and termed *ideal* to the sequence of images without any time delay and *real* as the delayed image sequence. All the acquired images are time stamped to verify the delay time manually in the complete data set. The obtained classification label at different instant (t) is shown in Fig. 8. At instant (t), the acquisition from (*Camera 1*), $x_{c,t}^1$ arrived and from (*Camera 2*) is delayed, $x_{c,t}^2$ will retain the previous acquisition at that time (t), until arrives the real acquisition of that camera as explain Fig. 7 and shown in Fig. 8. We estimated the evaluation parameters of classification at each time step (t) with Δ delay. Fig. 9 represents the obtained curve of cumulative accuracy of delayed signal with and without including the transition area. We observed over all reduced relative accuracy of 65% with the delayed signal which gradually fluctuate with increase in this delay. In terms of qualitative

analysis, if both camera system share the information to provide final consensus based output, the latency in data arrival directly influence the performance of the method. We presented this study as proof of concept for the effects of delayed transmission on independent or consensus based classification of moving objects. In the case of independent classification models, the delayed response is still manageable but in the case of consensus based real time evaluation, the acquisition arrived at the edge computing device with high latency deteriorate the complete litter monitoring process in real environment. As demonstrated in this study, the acquired data with single camera from different views identifies the same object incorrectly however with multi-camera system and by applying data fusion techniques, we can perform more reliable monitoring task on board.

Fig. 8. a) Classification at each instant without any delay (*Ideal* acquisition), b) Classification curve on delayed image sequences with Δ delay (*Real* acquisition), c) Classification curve on delayed image sequences with $2x\Delta$ (*Real* acquisition).

Fig. 9. Obtained accuracy curves with and without dotted area.

V. CONCLUSION

We employed low-latency transfer learning-based classification for marine litter objects with the aim of performing computation at the edge device without sending them for offline processing. With a test accuracy of 84% as a fixed feature extractor, ResNet50 performed independent classification of moving objects through a distributed camera system and performed computations in approximately real time near the computing device. We observed that the video stream from

different cameras arrives at the edge device with different delays, which decreases the accuracy, as the moving objects are incorrectly identified if viewed from another angle in real-time monitoring of litter objects. We also observed that the effect of illumination and environmental conditions at the time of data acquisition requires preprocessing, and higher latency is directly related to the network performance in the case of time-critical data. In the future, we intend to extend this study to consensus-based algorithms with more than two distributed camera systems and by integrating and sharing the information acquired from sensors through fusion-based algorithms to perform marine litter monitoring.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This study has been funded in part by PON “Ricerca –Innovazione” 2014–2020 and by the project CLEVER (Project ID 101097560), that is supported by the Key Digital Technologies Joint Undertaking and its members (including top-up funding by Italian Ministry of University and Research — MUR).

REFERENCES

- [1] Sheavly, S.; Register, K. “Marine debris plastics: Environmental concerns, sources, impacts and solutions“. *J. Polym. Environ.* 2007, 15, 301–305.
- [2] Marin, I.; Mladenović, S.; Gotovac, S.; Zaharija, G. “Deep-Feature-Based Approach to Marine Debris Classification.“ *Appl. Sci.* 2021, 11, 5644. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11125644>.
- [3] Miquel Canals et al. “The quest for seafloor macrolitter: a critical review of background knowledge, current methods and future prospects“, 2021 *Environ. Res. Lett.* 16 023001
- [4] M. Fulton, J. Hong, M. J. Islam and J. Sattar, “Robotic Detection of Marine Litter Using Deep Visual Detection Models,“ 2019 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA), 2019, pp. 5752-5758, doi: 10.1109/ICRA.2019.8793975.
- [5] Politikos, D., Fakiris, Elias, Davvetas, Athanasios, Klampanos, Iraklis, Papatheodorou, George. (2021). “ Automatic detection of seafloor marine litter using towed camera images and deep learning. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*“ . 164. 111974. 10.1016/j.marpolbul.2021.111974.
- [6] Marin, I.; Mladenović, S.; Gotovac, S.; Zaharija, G. “Deep-Feature-Based Approach to Marine Debris Classification.“ *Appl. Sci.* 2021, 11, 5644. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11125644>.
- [7] M. Valdenegro-Toro, “Submerged marine debris detection with autonomous underwater vehicles,“ 2016 International Conference on Robotics and Automation for Humanitarian Applications (RAHA), 2016, pp. 1-7, doi: 10.1109/RAHA.2016.7931907.
- [8] Colin van Lieshout, Kees van Oeveren, Tim van Emmerik, Eric Postma, “Automated River Plastic Monitoring Using Deep Learning and Cameras“. *Earth and Space Science*, Volume 7, Issue 8, August 2020.
- [9] B. Song, A. T. Kamal, C. Soto, C. Ding, J. A. Farrell and A. K. Roy-Chowdhury, “Tracking and Activity Recognition Through Consensus in Distributed Camera Networks,“ in *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 19, no. 10, pp. 2564-2579, Oct. 2010,
- [10] Previtali, F., Bloisi, D.D. Iocchi, L.“ A distributed approach for real time multi camera multiple object tracking,“ *Machine Vision and Applications* 28, 421–430 (2017).
- [11] Haiyun Guo et al. “Learning Multi-view Deep Features for Small Object Retrieval in Surveillance Scenarios.“ In *Proceedings of the 23rd ACM international conference on Multimedia*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 859–862.
- [12] JAMSTEC, <https://www.godac.jamstec.go.jp/bismal/e/dataset/JAMSTEC>
- [13] TrashNet, <https://github.com/garythung/trashnet>
- [14] Gu, J.; Wang, Z.; Kuen, J.; Ma, L.; Shahroudy, A.; Shuai, B.; Liu, T.; Wang, X.; Wang, G.; Cai, J.; et al. “Recent advances in convolutional neural networks.“ *Pattern Recognit.* 2018, 77, 354–377.
- [15] L., Joseph, B. Shabab, Corcoran, Peter, “Transfer Learning of Temporal Information for Driver Action Classification“, 2017.